

THE USE AND EFFECTS OF BORON IN STEEL ALLOYS

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In modern metallurgy and materials science, enhancing the properties of steel by adding various chemical elements is a common and widely used method. Among such elements, boron (B) occupies a significant place. When added in very small amounts (typically around 0.001–0.006%), boron can significantly improve the mechanical strength, hardness, and cold resistance of steel. These properties are especially valuable in the automotive industry, construction, military equipment, and mechanical engineering sectors [1,2].

The effects of boron on steel can be summarized as follows:

Effect on Microstructure. Boron influences the formation of ferrite and pearlite phases by concentrating at grain boundaries. This restricts the movement of particles and helps reduce the brittleness of steel.

Changes During Heat Treatment. As an alloying element, boron delays low-temperature phase transformations during solidification. This enhances the formation of martensitic structures during quenching and tempering processes, improving hardenability.

Corrosion Resistance. Even in small quantities, boron increases the oxidation resistance of steel. Especially when present as boron nitride or boron carbide, it helps form a passive protective layer on the surface, enhancing corrosion resistance.

Effect on Mechanical Properties. In boron-alloyed steels, ductility and flexibility are improved. Crack resistance and the ability to withstand crack propagation are enhanced. As a microalloying element, boron increases the hardness limit of steel [3-5].

The addition of even a small amount of boron fundamentally improves the mechanical, thermal, and chemical properties of steel. It enables the formation of structures that are high-strength, impact-resistant, hard, and heat-resistant. For this reason, boron is widely recognized as a cost-effective and highly efficient alloying element in steel production. Future research on boron-based nanocomposites and complex composite materials indicates that this field holds great potential for further development.

References

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